

Updated and annotated checklist of the opisthobranch molluscs (excluding Thecosomata and Gymnosomata) from the Azores archipelago (North Atlantic Ocean, Portugal)¹

Lista comentada y actualizada de los moluscos opistobranquios (excepto los Thecosomata y Gymnosomata) del archipiélago de las Azores (Océano Atlántico Norte, Portugal)¹

Manuel António Encarnação MALAQUIAS*

Recibido el 15-IX-2000. Aceptado el 18-I-2001

ABSTRACT

The literature available on the opisthobranch molluscs of the Azores archipelago is reviewed in this study. A critical discussion is done on some of the most recent papers concerning this subject. A summary of the opisthobranch species from the Azores is presented. The opisthobranch fauna (excluding the planctonic Thecosomata and Gymnosomata) comprises 107 identified species distributed among six orders, Cephalaspidea *s.l.*: 50, Anaspidea: 5, Tyrodinoidea: 2, Pleurobranchoidea: 6, Sacoglossa: 4 and Nudibranchia: 40.

RESUMEN

En el presente trabajo se ha hecho una revisión de la literatura existente sobre los moluscos opistobranquios del archipiélago de las Azores. Son discutidos los trabajos más recientes en relación con esta materia. Se incluye una sinopsis de las especies de opistobranquios de las Islas Azores. La fauna identificada (excluyendo las especies de los grupos planctónicos Thecosomata y Gymnosomata) comprende 107 especies que se distribuyen en seis órdenes, Cephalaspidea *s.l.*: 50, Anaspidea: 5, Tyrodinoidea: 2, Pleurobranchoidea: 6, Sacoglossa: 4 and Nudibranchia: 40.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Opisthobranchia, Azores, Atlantic Ocean, Portugal

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Opisthobranchia, Azores, Océano Atlántico, Portugal

INTRODUCTION

The first works concerning the Azorean opisthobranch molluscs are those by DROUËT (1858), WATSON (1883; 1886), SIMROTH (1888), DAUTZENBERG (1889), RUSH (1891), BERGH (1892), PILSBRY (1895), VAYSSIÈRE (1896), DAUT-

ZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896), LOCARD (1897) and BERGH (1899), based particularly on material collected during some scientific expeditions carried out during the last century, 'Challenger', 'Princesse Alice', 'L'Hirondelle' and 'Talisman'.

¹ Contribution of the Instituto Português de Malacologia

* Centro de Ciências do Mar, Faculdade de Ciências do Mar e do Ambiente, Universidade do Algarve, Campus de Gambelas, 8000 – 810 Faro, Portugal, tel. +351-289 800 900 (ext.7031), fax +351-289 818 353, email mmalaqui@ualg.pt

Besides the description of new species, based on specimens captured in Azores, those studies given an important contribution to testacean opisthobranch taxonomy (Cephalaspidea *s.l.*) as well as to that of non-testacean forms of the orders Pleurobranchoidea and Nudibranchia from the archipelago.

During the twentieth century, especially in the second half, many works have contributed considerably to the knowledge of opisthobranch molluscs from Azores (SYKES, 1904; NOBRE, 1924; ODHNER, 1931; EALES, 1957, 1960; MARCUS, 1967, 1970; NORDSIECK, 1972; BOUCHET, 1975; 1977; NORDSIECK AND GARCÍA-TALAVERA, 1979; GARCÍA-TALAVERA, 1983; GOSLINER, 1990; 1994; AZEVEDO AND GOFAS, 1990; AZEVEDO, 1991; MENEZES, 1991; WIRTZ, 1992; 1995; 1999; WIRTZ AND MARTINS, 1993; LINDEN, 1994; 1995; ORTEA, VALDÉS AND ESPINOSA, 1994; PICTON AND MORROW, 1994; JENSEN, 1995; MORO, ORTEA, BACALLADO, VALDÉS AND PÉREZ-SÁNCHEZ, 1995; ORTEA, VALDÉS AND GARCÍA-GÓMEZ, 1996A; ORTEA, BACALLADO, PÉREZ-SÁNCHEZ AND VALLÈS, 1996B; VALDÉS AND ORTEA, 1996; VALDÉS, ORTEA, ÁVILA AND BALLESTEROS, 1996; ÁVILA AND AZEVEDO, 1996; 1997; ÁVILA, AZEVEDO, GONÇALVES, FONTES AND CARDIGOS, 1998; MORTON, BRITTON AND MARTINS, 1998; ORTEA AND MORO, 1999 and ÁVILA, 2000).

Very recently, the opisthobranch molluscs of the Azores were the goal of MIKKELSEN (1995) and WIRTZ (1998). MIKKELSEN (1995) given the account of cephalaspidean species of the archipelago and reported the occurrence of forty-six species. This author described shells and provided anatomical details for several species, possible synonymies and misidentifications, and also discussed zoogeographical affinities. WIRTZ (1998) presented an updated summary of the opisthobranch gastropods (except the Cephalaspidea *s.l.*), with a record of sixteen new species.

The detailed analysis of these recent contributions shows that several species previously recorded from the Azores were not considered in MIKKELSEN

(1995) and WIRTZ (1998). The list of opisthobranch molluscs occurring in the Azores archipelago is completed in the present study by means of a comprehensive literature review.

RESULTS

Based on the analysis of the known literature, it can be noted that two species, *Philine rugulosa* Dautzenberg and Fischer, 1896 and *Philine intricata* Monterosato, 1884 were excluded from Mikkelsen's inventory of the azorean cephalaspids and twenty-two species previously mentioned for the coasts of the Azores islands, were not included in WIRTZ (1998): four Pleurobranchoidea, one Sacoglossa and seventeen Nudibranchia (see species with an asterisk in the appendix). Four species previously mentioned, were referred to by Wirtz as first references for the archipelago. A complete taxonomic list of the opisthobranch species from the Azores is presented in an appendix.

DISCUSSION

Previous studies (BERGH, 1892, 1899; BOUCHET, 1977; AZEVEDO AND GOFAS, 1990; AZEVEDO, 1991; LINDEN, 1994; ORTEA *ET AL.* 1996A; VALDÉS AND ORTEA, 1996; ÁVILA AND AZEVEDO, 1997 and MORTON *ET AL.* 1998), mentioned opisthobranch species for the Azores not included in WIRTZ (1998) account. Even one genus (*Thorybopus*) and five species (*P. morosus*, *K. atlanticus*, *H. goslineri*, *P. stomascuta*, and *T. lophatus*) for which the Azores is the type-locality were not considered.

On the the contrary WIRTZ (1998) claimed first records of species already mentioned in the literature. This was the case of *Fionna pinnata*, cited by BERGH (1892: 6) as *Fiona marina*, *Geitodoris planata*, recorded by AZEVEDO AND GOFAS (1990: 86), *Flabellina pedata*, cited by GOSLINER (1994) and *Marionia blainvillae*, recorded by the author himself (WIRTZ, 1995: 182).

Among the species of opisthobranchs recorded from the Azores, eight have not been identified at species level. GOSLINER (1990) mentioned the occurrence of *Runcina* sp. noting that, with the exception of the body coloration, the specimens are anatomically similar to the species *R. coronata*, which leads the author to the hypothesis that the studied specimens may be conspecific with this species. However, given the present lack of a revision of this group showing the intra-specific and inter-specific variation among different geographic regions, the author decided not to attribute the specimens to any particular species. Although the anterior situation has not yet been altered, ORTEA AND MORO (1999) describe the species *Runcina hidalgoensis* based on specimens which were collected in the Canaries and Azores, similar to those studied by GOSLINER (1990).

BOUCHET (1977) referred to an undetermined species of the genus *Platydoris* externally similar to *Platydoris stomascuta*, but with marked differences in the digestive and genital organs and also to other two specimens of the family Dorididae. After the anatomical study of these two dorids, the author concludes that identification is difficult considering the fact that these are the only specimens, collected at great depth (more than 1000 m) and that the external morphological characteristics may have suffered damage along the sampling procedures (BOUCHET 1977: 42-43 and 46-48).

WIRTZ (1998) based solely on the external morphology, distinguished four undetermined species from the Azores

(one sacoglossan and three nudibranchs). However, the assumption that specimens with small external morphological differences belong to different species can lead to misconceptions, once the biological species concept admits the existence of intra-specific variability. E.g. specimens of the genus *Tambja* were regarded as two different species: *Tambja* sp. (WIRTZ 1998: pl. 5, fig.6, p. 14) and *Tambja ceutae* (WIRTZ 1998: pl. 5, fig.5, pag.14). Despite the chromatic differences between specimens observed by WIRTZ (1998) a more detailed study of the morphology and coloration of the mantle tubercles and radula (Cervera and Malaquias, unpublished data), revealed the existence of two distinct chromatic forms for *Tambja ceutae* and not two different species as suggested by Wirtz.

The opisthobranch molluscs of the Azores (excluding the planctonic Thecosomata and Gymnosomata) comprise a total of 107 identified species distributed as follows: Cephalaspidea s.l.: 50, Anaspidea: 5, Tyrodinoidea: 2, Pleurobranchioidea: 6, Sacoglossa: 4 and Nudibranchia: 40.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I wish to thank my friends and colleagues Alexandra Marques, Jeff Wallace, Eduardo Esteves and Anxo Conde (Universidade do Algarve), Ilidio Félix-Alves (Instituto Português de Malacologia) and Sérgio Ávila (Universidade dos Açores), for their suggestions that improved this paper.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ÁVILA, S. P., 2000. Shallow-water marine molluscs of the Azores: biogeographical relationships. *Arquipélago. Life and Marine Sciences*, Supplement 2 (1): 99-130.
- ÁVILA, S. AND AZEVEDO, J. M. N., 1996. Checklist of the marine molluscs of the littoral of Pico Island (Azores, Portugal). *Libro de Resúmenes XI Congreso Nacional de Malacología. Sociedad Española de Malacología*: 106-107.
- ÁVILA, S. AND AZEVEDO, J. M. N., 1997. Shallow-water molluscs from the Formigas Islets. Azores, collected during the "Santa Maria e Formigas 1990" Scientific Expedition. *Açoreana*, 8 (3): 323-330.
- ÁVILA, S., AZEVEDO, J. M. N., GONÇALVES, J. M., FONTES, J. AND CARDIGOS, F., 1998. Checklist of the shallow-water marine molluscs of the Azores: 1 – Pico, Faial, Flores and Corvo. *Açoreana*, 8 (4): 487-523.

- AZEVEDO, J. M. N., 1991. Moluscos litorais da ilha de Santa Maria. Santa Maria e Formigas/1990. *Relatórios e Comunicações Científicas do Departamento de Biologia*, 19: 43-46.
- AZEVEDO, J. M. N. AND GOFAS, S., 1990. Moluscos marinhos litorais da ilha das Flores. Expedição Científica Flores/89 (relatório preliminar). *Relatórios e Comunicações Científicas do Departamento de Biologia*, 18: 83-87.
- BERGH, L. S. R., 1892. Opisthobranches provenant des campagnes du yacht l'Hirondelle. *Résultats des Campagnes Scientifiques accomplies sur son Yacht par Albert Ier Prince souverain de Monaco*. Fascicule IV: 1-35.
- BERGH, L. S. R., 1899. Nudibranchs et Marsenia provenant des campagnes de la «Princesse Alice» (1891-1897). *Résultats des Campagnes Scientifiques accomplies sur son yacht par Albert Ier prince souverain de Monaco*, Fascicule XIV: 1-45p.
- BOUCHET, P., 1975. Opisthobranches de profondeur de l'océan Atlantique. I – Cephalaspidea. *Cahiers de Biologie Marine*, 16: 317-365.
- BOUCHET, P., 1977. Opisthobranches de profondeur de l'océan Atlantique: II – Notaspidea et Nudibranchiata. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 43: 28-66.
- CERVERA, J. L., GARCÍA-GÓMEZ, J. C. AND GARCÍA, F. J., 1991. The genus *Runcina* Forbes and Hanley, 1851 (Opisthobranchia: Cephalaspidea) in the Strait of Gibraltar, with the description of a new species from the Bay of Algeciras. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 57: 199-208.
- DAUTZENBERG, P., 1889. Révision des mollusques marins des Açores. Contribution à la faune malacologique des Iles Açores. Résultats des dragages effectués par le yacht l'Hirondelle pendant sa campagne scientifique de 1887. *Résultats des campagnes scientifiques, accomplies sur son yacht par Albert Ier Prince Souverain de Monaco*, I: 1-112, pls. I-IV.
- DAUTZENBERG, P. AND FISCHER, H., 1896. Campagnes scientifiques de S. A. le Prince Albert Ier de Monaco. Dragages effectués par l'Hirondelle et par la Princesse-Alice, 1888-1895. *Mémoires de la Société Zoologique de France*, IX: 395-498, Pls. XV-XXII.
- DAUTZENBERG, P. AND FISCHER, H., 1897. Campagnes scientifiques de S. A. le Prince Albert Ier de Monaco. Dragages effectués par l'Hirondelle et par la Princesse-Alice, 1888-1896. *Mémoires de la Société Zoologique de France*, X: 139-234, Pls. III-VII.
- DROUËT, H., 1858. Molusques marins des îles Açores. *Mémoires de la Société d'Agriculture du Département de l'Aube*, 22: 1-53.
- EALLES, N. B., 1957. Revision of the species of *Aplysia* of the Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (Malacologie), Paris. *Bulletin du Muséum*, 2^e série, t. XXIX, n^o3: 246-255.
- EALLES, N. B., 1960. Revision of the world species of *Aplysia* (Gastropoda: Opisthobranchia). *Bulletin of the British Museum (Natural History) (Zoology)*, 5 (10): 267-404.
- GARCÍA-TALAVERA, C. F., 1983 (1981). *Los moluscos gasteropodos anfiatlánticos (estudio paleo y biogeográfico de las especies bentónicas litorales)*. Universidad de la Laguna, Secretariado Publicaciones, Colección Monográficas, No.10, 352p.
- GOSLINER, T. M., 1990. Opisthobranch mollusks from the Azores Islands. I. Runcinidae and Chromodorididae. *Açoreana*, Suplemento 1990: 135-166.
- GOSLINER, T. M., 1994. New records of Flabellinidae (Opisthobranchia: Aeolidacea) from the Tropical Americas, with descriptions of two new species. *Proceedings of the California Academy of Sciences*, 48 (9): 171-183.
- JENSEN, K. R., 1995. Anatomy and Biology of *Aplysiopsis formosa* Pruvot-Fol (Mollusca, Opisthobranchia, Sacoglossa) from the Azores. *Açoreana*, Suplemento 1995: 217-230.
- LINDEN, J. VAN DER, 1994. *Philine intricata* Monterosato, 1884, an overlooked species from the North-East Atlantic and the Mediterranean Sea (Gastropoda, Opisthobranchia, Philinidae). *Basteria*, 58: 41-48.
- LINDEN, J. VAN DER, 1995. Philinidae dredged by the CANCAP expeditions (Gastropoda, Opisthobranchia). *Basteria*, 59: 65-83.
- LOCARD, A., 1897. *Expéditions scientifiques du «Travailleur» et du «Talisman», pendant les années 1880, 1881, 1882, 1883. Molusques testacés*. Masson et Cie, Paris, 512pp.
- MARCUS, E. D. B.-R., 1967. Opisthobranchs from the southwestern Caribbean Sea. *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 17 (3): 597-628.
- MARCUS, E. D. B.-R., 1970. Opisthobranchs from northern Brazil. *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 20 (4): 922-951.
- MENEZES, G., 1991. *Umbraculum mediterraneum* (Lamarck, 1819) (Mollusca: Opisthobranchia: Umbraculomorpha), a new record for the littoral fauna of the Azores. *Arquipélago. Life and Marine Sciences*, 9: 101-102.
- MILLEN, S.V. AND GOSLINER, T. M., 1985. Four new species of dorid nudibranchs belonging to the genus *Aldisa* (Mollusca, Opisthobranchia), with a revision of the genus. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 84 (3): 195-233.
- MIKKELSEN, P. M., 1995. Cephalaspid opisthobranchs of the Azores. *Açoreana*, Suplemento 1995: 193-215.
- MORO, L., ORTEA, J., BACALLADO, J., VALDÉS, A. AND PÉREZ-SÁNCHEZ, J. M., 1995. Nuevos aeolidáceos (Gastropoda, Nudibranchia) para la fauna de Canarias. *Revista de la Academia Canaria de Ciencias*, 7 (2, 3 y 4): 63-75.

- MORTON, B., BRITTON, J. C. AND MARTINS, A. M. F., 1998. *Ecologia Costeira dos Açores*, Sociedade Afonso Chaves, Associação de Estudos Açoreanos, 249pp.
- NOBRE, A., 1924. Contribuições para a fauna dos Açores. *Anais do Instituto de Zoologia*, Universidade do Porto, 1: 41-90.
- NORDSIECK, F., 1972. *Die europäischen Meeresschnecken (Opisthobranchia mit Pyramidellidae; Rissoacea) vom Eismeer bis Kapverden, Mittelmeer und Schwarzes Meer*, Gustav Fischer Verlag, Stuttgart, 327pp.
- NORDSIECK, F. AND GARCÍA-TALavera, F., 1979. *Moluscos marinos de Canarias y Madera (Gastropoda)*, Aula de Cultura de Tenerife, 208pp, 46pls.
- ODHNER, N. H., 1931. Beiträge zur Malakozoologie der Kanarischen Inseln Lamelibranchen, Cephalopoden, Gastropoden. *Arkiv för Zoologi*, Stockholm, 23A: 1-116.
- ORTEA, J., VALDÉS, Á. AND ESPINOSA, J., 1994. North Atlantic nudibranchs of the *Chromodoris clenchi* colour group (Opisthobranchia: Chromodorididae). *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 60: 237-248.
- ORTEA, J., VALDÉS, A. AND GARCÍA-GÓMEZ, J. C., 1996a. Review of the Atlantic species of the family Chromodorididae (Mollusca: Nudibranchia) of the blue chromatic group. *Avicennia*, Suplemento 1: 1-165.
- ORTEA, J., MORO, L., BACALLADO, J. J., PÉREZ-SÁNCHEZ, J. M. AND VALLÉS, Y., 1996b. Nuevos datos sobre la fauna de dóridos fanerobranquios (Gastropoda, Nudibranchia) de las Islas Canarias. *Revista de la Academia Canaria de Ciencias*, 8 (2, 3 y 4): 125-138.
- ORTEA, J., MORO, L., BACALLADO, J. J. AND ESPINOSA, J., 1998. Catálogo abreviado de las especies del orden Sacoglossa (=Ascoglossa, Mollusca: Opisthobranchia) de las islas Canarias y de Cabo Verde. *Revista de la Academia Canaria de las Ciencias*, 10 (número 4): 85-96.
- ORTEA, J. AND MORO, L., 1999. Estudio de las especies del género *Runcina* Forbes y Hanley, 1853 (Opisthobranchia: Cephalaspidea) de coloración rojiza (grupo "ferruginea") en la Macaronesia, con la descripción de tres especies nuevas. *Revista de la Academia Canaria de las Ciencias*, 11 (Núms. 3-4): 63-74.
- PICTON, B. E. AND MORROW, C. C., 1994. *A field guide to the nudibranchs of the British Isles*. Immel Publishing Limited, London, 143p
- PILSBRY, H. A., 1895. Polyplacophora. Acantochitonidae, Cryptoplacidae and appendix. Tectibranchiata. *Manual of Conchology* (1), 15 (60): 181-436.
- RUSH, W. H., 1891. List of shells collected on Fayal Islands, Azores; and on Madeira Islands; with prefatory notes. *The Nautilus*, 5 (5): 49-52.
- SIMROTH, H., 1888. Zur Kenntnis der Azorenfauna. *Arch. für Naturg.* Berlin, 54 (1): 179-234.
- SYKES, E. R., 1904. Mollusca of the 'Porcupine' expeditions, 1869-70. Part I. *Proceedings of the Malacological Society of London*, 6 (1): 23-40.
- VALDÉS, A. AND ORTEA, J., 1996. Review of the family Phyllidiidae in the Atlantic Ocean (Nudibranchia, Doridoidea). *American Malacological Bulletin*, 13 (1/2): 1-9.
- VALDÉS, A., ORTEA, J., ÁVILA, C. AND BALLESTEROS, M., 1996. Review of the genus *Dendrodoris* Ehrenberg, 1831 (Gastropoda: Nudibranchia) in the Atlantic Ocean. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 62: 1-31
- VAYSSIÈRE, A., 1896. Description des coquilles des quelques espèces nouvelles ou peu connues de Pleurobranchides. *Journal de Conchyliologie*, 44: 113-137.
- VAYSSIÈRE, A., 1902. Opisthobranches, in *Expéditions scientifiques du «Travailleur» et du «Talisman» pendant les années 1880, 1881, 1882, 1883*. Masson et Cie Editeurs, Paris, 221-270, Pls. IX-XI.
- WATSON, R. B., 1883. Mollusca of H. M. S. Challenger, Pt. XIX. *Journal of the Linnean Society of London, Zoology*, 17 (101): 319-340; 17 (20): 341-346.
- WATSON, R. B., 1886. Report on the Scaphopoda and Gasteropoda collected by H.M.S. Challenger during the years 1873-1876. *Report on the Scientific Results of the Voyage of H. M. S. Challenger during the years 1873-76*. Zoology. 17 (II), i-v+1-756, Pls. I-LIII.
- WIRTZ, P., 1992. Pleurobranchier von der Azoren. *Die Aquarien und Terrarien Zeitschrift (DATS)*, 1992 (1): 45-46.
- WIRTZ, P., 1994. Three shrimps, five nudibranchs, and two tunicates new for the marine fauna of Madeira. *Boletim do Museu Municipal do Funchal*, 46 (257): 167-172.
- WIRTZ, P., 1995. *Unterwasserführer Madeira Kanaren / Azoren, Niedere Tiere*, Delius Klasing, Edition Nagelschmid, 247pp.
- WIRTZ, P., 1998. Opisthobranch molluscs from the Azores. *Vita Marina*, 45 (1-2): 1-16.
- WIRTZ, P., 1999. *Hydatina physis* (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Opisthobranchia) from the Azores. *Arquipélago*. Life and Marine Sciences, 17A: 97-99.
- WIRTZ, P. AND MARTINS, H., 1993. Notes on some rare and little known marine invertebrates from the Azores, with a discussion on the zoogeography of the area. *Arquipélago*, Life and Marine Science, 11A, 55-63.

Appendix – Synopsis of the opisthobranch molluscs from the Azores
Apéndice – Sinopsis de los moluscos opisthobranquios de las Azores

Order CEPHALASPIDEA s.l. Fischer, 1883

Family Ringiculidae Meeck, 1862

Ringicula blanchardi Dautzenberg and Fischer, 1896

DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896, 1897), MIKKELSEN (1995).

Ringicula semistriata Orbigny, 1853

NORDSIECK (1972), MIKKELSEN (1995).

Family Acteonidae D'Orbigny, 1835

Acteon incisus Dall, 1881

DAUTZENBERG AND FISHER (1896), MIKKELSEN (1995).

Acteon monterosatoi Dautzenberg, 1889

DAUTZENBERG (1889), DAUTZENBERG AND FISHER (1896, 1897), NORDSIECK [1972 as *Acteon (Metacteon)*], MIKKELSEN (1995).

Acteonina amabilis (Watson, 1883)

WATSON (1883, 1886 in both works as *Acteon*), DAUTZENBERG (1889 as *Acteon*), DAUTZENBERG AND FISHER (1897 as *Acteon*), NORDSIECK [1972 as *Callostracon (Ovacteonina)*], MIKKELSEN (1995).

Acteonina chariis (Watson, 1883)

WATSON (1883, 1886 in both works as *Acteon*), DAUTZENBERG (1889 as *Acteon*), DAUTZENBERG AND FISHER (1897 as *Acteon (Acteonina)*), NORDSIECK [1972 as *Callostracon (Ovacteonina)*], MIKKELSEN (1995).

Crenilabium exilis (Jeffreys, 1870)

DAUTZENBERG (1889 as *Acteon*), DAUTZENBERG AND FISHER (1896, 1897 in both works as *Acteon (Lisacteon)*), WATSON (1886 as *Acteon*), NORDSIECK (1972 as *Crenilabrum*), MIKKELSEN (1995).

Inopinodon azoricus (Locard, 1897)

LOCARD (1897), BOUCHET (1975), MIKKELSEN (1995).

?*Japonacteon pusillus* (Forbes, 1843)

BOUCHET (1975), MIKKELSEN (1995).

Liocarenum ?globulinus (Forbes, 1843)

WATSON (1886 as *Acteon*). The identification made by Watson was based on a shell fragment collected at 1828 m, DAUTZENBERG (1889 as *Acteon*), NORDSIECK (1972), MIKKELSEN (1995).

Mysouffa turritus (Watson, 1886)

BOUCHET (1975), DAUTZENBERG AND FISHER (1896 as *Acteon grimaldii*), MIKKELSEN (1995).

Ovulactaeon meeki Dall, 1889

NORDSIECK (1972), MIKKELSEN (1995).

Family Hydatinidae Pilsbry, 1893

Hydatina physis (Gmelin, 1794)

WIRTZ (1999)

Micromelo undatus (Bruguière, 1792)

NORDSIECK (1972), GARCÍA-TALAVERA (1983), MIKKELSEN (1995).

Family Diaphanidae Odhner, 1914

Diaphana seguenzae (Watson, 1886)

WATSON (1886), DAUTZENBERG (1889 as *Amphisphyra*), NORDSIECK (1972 as *Toledonia seguenzae*), MIKKELSEN (1995).

Family Retusidae Thiele, 1926

Pyrrunculus ovatus (Jeffreys, 1870)

BOUCHET (1975), MIKKELSEN (1995).

- Relichna simplex* (Locard, 1897)
BOUCHET (1975), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Retusa leuca* (Watson, 1883)
WATSON (1883, 1886 in both works as *Utriculus leucus*), DAUTZENBERG (1889 as *Tornatina*), NORDSIECK (1972), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Retusa truncatula* (Bruguière, 1792)
DAUTZENBERG (1889 as *Tornatina truncatula* and also as *Tornatina mariei* n.sp.), NORDSIECK [1972 as *Retusa (Coleophysis) mariei*], NORDSIECK AND GARCÍA-TALAVERA (1979 as *Retusa mariae*), MIKKELSEN (1995), MORTON ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Retusa multiquadrata* Oberling, 1970
MIKKELSEN (1995), MORTON ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998).
- Cylichnina umbilicata* (Montagu, 1803)
ÁVILA AND AZEVEDO (1996), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998,), ÁVILA (2000).
- Family Cylichnidae Rudman, 1978
- Acteocina protracta* (Dautzenberg, 1889)
DAUTZENBERG (1889 as *Tornatina*), DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896, 1897 both works as *Tornatina*), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- "*Bulla*" *semilaevis* Seguenza, 1879
WATSON (1886 as *Bulla*), DAUTZENBERG (1889 as *Bulla guernei* and also as *Bulla semilaevis*), DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896, 1897 both works as *Bulla guernei*), NORDSIECK [1972 as *Bulla (Leucophysena)*], MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Cylichna alba* (Brown, 1827)
WATSON (1886), SYKES (1904), NORDSIECK (1972), MIKKELSEN (1995), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998).
- Cylichna chevreuxi* Dautenberg, 1889
DAUTZENBERG (1889), DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896, 1897), NORDSIECK (1972), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Cylichna cylindracea* (Pennant, 1777)
PILSBRY (1895), SYKES (1904), NORDSIECK (1972), MIKKELSEN (1995), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Cylichna oliviformis* (Watson, 1883)
WATSON (1883, 1886 in both works as *Utriculus*), DAUTZENBERG (1889 as *Tornatina*), DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896, 1897 in both works as *Utriculus*), NORDSIECK (1972 as *Cylichnium*), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Cylichna ovata* Jeffreys, 1871
WATSON (1886), DAUTZENBERG (1889), DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896, 1897), LOCARD (1897), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Cylichna piettei* Dautzenberg and Fisher, 1896
DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896, 1897), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Mamillocylichna richardi* Dautzenberg, 1889
DAUTZENBERG (1889 as *Cylichna richardi*), DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1897 as *Cylichna*), NORDSIECK (1972), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Meloscaplander imperceptus* Bouchet, 1975
BOUCHET (1975), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Roxania monterosatoi* Dautzenberg and Fischer, 1896
DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896, 1897), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Scaphander gracilis* Watson, 1883
WATSON (1883, 1886), DAUTZENBERG (1889), DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896, 1897), LOCARD (1897), NORDSIECK (1972), BOUCHET (1975), MIKKELSEN (1995).

- Scaphander nobilis* Verrill, 1884
BOUCHET (1975), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Scaphander punctostriatus* (Mighels, 1841)
WATSON (1886), DAUTZENBERG (1889), DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896, 1897), LOCARD (1897), NORDSIECK (1972), BOUCHET (1975), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Family Philinidae Gray, 1850
- Philine approximans* Dautzenberg and Fischer, 1896
DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896, 1897), BOUCHET (1975), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Philine azorica* Bouchet, 1975
BOUCHET (1975), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Philine ?lima* Brown, 1827
DAUTZENBERG (1889), NORDSIECK (1972), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Philine monilifera* Bouchet, 1975
BOUCHET (1975), MIKKELSEN (1995), LINDEN (1995 as *P. cf. monilifera*).
- Philine quadrata* (S. Wood, 1839)
WATSON (1886), DAUTZENBERG (1889), NORDSIECK [1972 as *Laona (Ossiana)*], MIKKELSEN (1995); LINDEN (1995), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Philine rugulosa* Dautzenberg and Fischer, 1896
DAUTZENBERG AND FISCHER (1896).
- Philine intricata* Monterosato, 1884
LINDEN (1994; 1995).
- Philine calva* Linden, 1995
LINDEN (1995)
- Philine condensa* Linden, 1995
LINDEN (1995)
- Family Runcinidae H. and Adams, 1854
- Runcina adriatica* Thompson, 1980
GOSLINER (1990), MIKKELSEN (1995), ÁVILA (2000).
- Runcina coronata* (Quatrefages, 1844)
GOSLINER (1990), MIKKELSEN (1995), ÁVILA (2000). All these authors refer to this species as *R. aurata* García, Lopez, Luque and Cervera, 1986 that is a junior synonym of *R. coronata*. For a discussion of this subject see CERVERA ET AL. (1991: 200-201).
- Runcina hidalgoensis* Ortea and Moro, 1999
GOSLINER (1990), MIKKELSEN (1995), ÁVILA (2000) all these authors as *Runcina* sp.. ORTEA AND MORO (1999: 67), São Miguel, Azores.
- Family Bullidae Lamarck, 1801
- Bulla pinguicula* Watson, 1886
WATSON (1886), DAUTZENBERG (1889), NORDSIECK (1972 as *Roxania*), MIKKELSEN (1995).
- Bulla striata* Bruguière, 1792
DROUËT (1858), DAUTZENBERG (1889), RUSH (1891), NORDSIECK (1972), GARCÍA-TALAVERA (1983), MIKKELSEN (1995), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Family Haminoeidae Pilsbry, 1895
- Atys macandrewii* E. A. Smith, 1872
MARCUS (1970), NORDSIECK [1972 as *Atys (Limulatys)*], GARCÍA-TALAVERA (1983), MIKKELSEN (1995), ÁVILA (2000).
- Haminoea hydatis* (Linné, 1758)
GARCÍA-TALAVERA (1983), MIKKELSEN (1995), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998 as *H. cf. hydatis*), ÁVILA (2000).

MALACQUIAS: Checklist of the opisthobranch molluscs from the Azores

- Haminoea ortei* Talavera, Murillo and Templado, 1987
MIKKELSEN (1995), MORTON ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Order ANASPIDEA Fischer, 1883
- Family Akeridae Pilsbry, 1893
- Akera bullata* Müller, 1776
NOBRE (1924), ÁVILA (2000).
- Family Aplysiidae, Lamarck, 1809
- Aplysia parvula* Guilding in Mörch, 1863
EALES (1960), WIRTZ (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998).
- Aplysia depilans* Gmelin, 1791
AZEVEDO AND GOFAS (1990 as *Aplysia* sp), WIRTZ (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Aplysia fasciata* Poiret, 1789
WIRTZ AND MARTINS (1993), ÁVILA AND AZEVEDO (1997), WIRTZ (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Aplysia punctata* Cuvier, 1803
SIMROTH (1888), ÁVILA AND AZEVEDO (1997), WIRTZ (1998), MORTON ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Order TYLODINOIDEA Gray, 1847
- Family Tylodinidae Gray, 1847
- Tyrodina perversa* (Gmelin, 1791)
DAUTZENBERG (1889 as *Tyrodina citrina*), WIRTZ (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Family Umbraculidae Dall, 1889
- Umbraculum umbraculum* (Lightfoot, 1876)
MENEZES (1991), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Order PLEUROBRANCHOIDEA Férussac, 1822
- Family Pleurobranchidae Férussac, 1822
- Pleurobranchus testudinarius* Cantraine, 1836
WIRTZ AND MARTINS (1993), WIRTZ (1992, 1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- **Pleurobranchaea morosa* (Bergh, 1892)
BERGH (1892: 28 as *Pleurobranchillus morosus*). Type-locality channel Pico-Faial, 130 m depth.
- **Pleurobranchaea meckelli* Blainville, 1825
BERGH (1899: 26). Near Terceira island, 599m depth.
- **Berthella plumula* (Montagu, 1803)
BERGH (1892: 19, 1899: 27 as *Pleurobranchus plumula*). Channel Pico-Faial, 130 m depth.
- **Berthella aurantiaca* (Risso, 1818)
BERGH (1892: 26 as *Pleurobranchus aurantiacus*). Channel Pico-Faial, 130 m depth.
- Berthellina edwardsi* (Vayssière, 1896)
VAYSSIÈRE (1896: 1902), AZEVEDO AND GOFAS (1990 AS *BERTHELLINA* SP.), WIRTZ (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Order SACOGLOSSA Ihering, 1876
- Family Plakobranichidae Gray, 1840
- Elysia ornata* (Swainson, 1840)
WIRTZ (1995, 1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- **Elysia viridis* (Montagu, 1804)
AZEVEDO (1991: 27), ÁVILA (2000). Santa Maria island.

- Family Hermaeidae H. and A. Adams, 1854
Aplysiopsis formosa Pruvot-Fol, 1953
JENSEN (1995), WIRTZ (1998); ORTEA, ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Family Limapontiidae Gray, 1847
Placida verticillata Ortea, 1981
ÁVILA (2000).
Placida sp.
(see WIRTZ, 1998: 3), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998).
- Order NUDIBRANCHIA Blainville, 1814
- Family Onchidorididae Alder and Hancock, 1845
Diaphorodoris luteocincta (M. Sars, 1870)
WIRTZ AND MARTINS (1993), WIRTZ (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Family Triophidae Odhner, 1941
Kaloplocamus ramosus (Cantraine, 1835)
WIRTZ (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
**Kaloplocamus atlanticus* (Bergh, 1892)
BERGH (1892: 12, 1899: 19 as *Euplocamus atlanticus*), NORDSIECK (1972 as *Kaloplocamus ramosus* f. *atlanticus*). Type-locality channel Pico-Faial, 130 m depth.
- Family Polyceridae Alder and Hancock, 1845
Tambja ceutae García-Gómez and Ortea, 1988
WIRTZ AND MARTINS (1993), ORTEA ET AL. (1996b), WIRTZ (1995 as *Tambja ceutae* and also as *Roboastra europea*), WIRTZ (1998 as *Tambja ceutae* and as *Tambja* sp.), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998) and ÁVILA (2000) as *Tambja ceutae* and as *Tambja* sp..
Limacia clavigera (Müller, 1776)
WIRTZ (1998), ORTEA ET AL. (1996b), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
Polycera elegans (Bergh, 1894)
WIRTZ AND MARTINS (1993), WIRTZ (1998), ORTEA ET AL. (1996b), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
Polycera quadrilineata (Müller, 1776)
WIRTZ (1998), ORTEA ET AL. (1996b), MORTON ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Polyceratidae indet.
(see WIRTZ, 1998: 13).
- Family Chromodorididae Bergh, 1891
Chromodoris britoi Ortea and Pérez, 1983
(see GOSLINER, 1990 [as *C. clenchi*]: 148, ORTEA ET AL., 1994 and WIRTZ, 1998: 8 for a discussion on this species), WIRTZ (1994; 1995), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (1999).
Chromodoris purpurea (Risso in Guérin, 1831)
GOSLINER (1990), WIRTZ (1994; 1995; 1998), MORTON ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
Chromodoris krohni (Vérany, 1846)
ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
**Chromodoris goslineri* Ortea and Valdés, 1996
ORTEA ET AL. (1996a: 143). Type-locality Santa Maria island.
Hypselodoris picta (Schultz in Philippi, 1836).
This species was recorded for the first time from Azores by BERGH (1899: 7) as *Chromodoris cantrainei*. GOSLINER (1990: 155) recorded to it as *H. webbi* and ORTEA ET AL. (1996a: 56 as *H. picta azorica*) and WIRTZ (1994 as *H. webbi*; 1998: 8 as *H. picta azorica*). ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).

MALACQUIAS: Checklist of the opisthobranch molluscs from the Azores

Hypselodoris fontandraui (Pruvot-Fol, 1951)

WIRTZ (1995, 1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).

Hypselodoris midatlantica Gosliner, 1990

[see GOSLINER, 1990: 152], ORTEA ET AL., 1996a: 32 and WIRTZ, 1998: 9 for a discussion on this species). ÁVILA ET AL (1998: 504), ÁVILA (2000). This species is usually mentioned under the name *H. tricolor*.

Glossodoris edmundsi Cervera, García-Gómez and Ortea, 1989

GOSLINER (1990), WIRTZ (1995, 1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).

Family Aldisidae Odhner, 1939

**Aldisa zetlandica* (Alder and Hancock, 1854)

BERGH (1899: 8), NORDSIECK (1972), PICTON AND MORROW (1994). Azores 38° 30' 30" N-38° 31' N and 29° 09' 30" W-29° 10' 30" W, 845 m depth.

Aldisa smaragdina Ortea, Pérez and Llera, 1982

WIRTZ (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998: 504), ÁVILA (2000). S. Ávila, cited this species as *A. binotata* according to the synonymy proposed by MILLEN AND GOSLINER (1985).

Family Dorididae Rafinesque, 1815

**Doris ocelligera* (Bergh, 1881)

AZEVEDO AND GOFAS (1990: 86), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998: 504), ÁVILA (2000). Azores, Flores island.

**Thorybopus lophatus* Bouchet, 1977

BOUCHET (1977: 43). Azores type-locality 37° 37' N-25° 32' W, 395-465 m depth.

*Dorididae sp.1

BOUCHET (1977). See BOUCHET (1977: 46) for a discussion on this species. Azores 37° 57' N-25° 33' W, 1070-1235 m depth.

*Dorididae sp.2

BOUCHET (1977). See BOUCHET (1977: 47) for a discussion on this species. Azores 37° 57' N-25° 33' W, 330 m depth.

Family Discodorididae Bergh, 1891

Discodoris atromaculata (Bergh, 1880)

WIRTZ AND MARTINS (1993), WIRTZ (1994; 1995, 1998), MORTON ET AL (1998 as *Peltodoris atromaculata*), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).

**Discodoris tristis* Bergh, 1892

BERGH (1899: 11). Ponta Delgada, São Miguel island, 98 m depth.

**Discodoris* cf. *millegrana* (Alder and Hancock, 1854)

ÁVILA AND AZEVEDO (1997: 328), ÁVILA (2000: appendix), Azores, Formigas Islets. According to Ávila (personal communication) this was a misidentification with an unknown species.

Geitodoris planata (Alder and Hancock, 1846)

AZEVEDO AND GOFAS (1990 as *Geitodoris* cf. *planata*), WIRTZ (1998), ÁVILA ET AL (1998), ÁVILA (2000).

Family Kentroborididae Bergh, 1892

**Jorunna tomentosa* (Cuvier, 1804)

MORTON ET AL. (1998: 151).

Family Platydorididae Bergh, 1891

Platydoris argo (Linné, 1767)

BERGH (1899), WIRTZ AND MARTINS (1993), WIRTZ (1994; 1998), ÁVILA ET AL (1998), ÁVILA (2000).

**Platydoris stomascuta* Bouchet, 1977

BOUCHET (1977: 35). Azores 37° 43' N-29° 04' W, 370-450 m depth.

- **Platydorís* sp.
BOUCHET (1977). See BOUCHET (1977: 42) for a discussion on this species.
Azores 37° 39' N-25° 35' W, 330 m depth.
- Taringa* sp.
(see WIRTZ, 1998: 12).
- Family Phyllidiidae Rafinesque, 1815
- **Phyllidiopsis berghi* Vayssière, 1902
BOUCHET [1977: 48 cited this species as *P. gynenopla* but according to VALDÉS AND ORTEA (1996: 3), it is a synonym of *P. berghi*], VALDÉS AND ORTEA (1996).
Azores 38° 22' -28° 48W, 525-600 m depth.
- **Reticulidia gofasi* Valdés and Ortea, 1996
VALDÉS AND ORTEA (1996: 7). Azores 38° 30' 00' N-27° 14' 05" W, 75-106 m depth.
- Family Dendrodorididae O'Donoghue, 1924
- **Dendrodoris limbata* (Cuvier, 1804)
BERGH (1892: 16 as *Doriopsis limbata*). Channel Pico-Faial, 130 m depth.
- Dendrodoris herytra* Valdés and Ortea, 1996
ODHNER (1931 as *D. grandiflora*), VALDÉS ET AL. (1996), WIRTZ (1995 as *Dendrodoris* n.sp., 1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Family Tritoniidae Lamarck, 1809
- **Tritonia (Tritonidoxa) griegi* Odhner, 1922
BOUCHET (1977: 53). Azores 47° 46' N – 8° 04' W, 820-940 m depth.
- Marionia blainvillea* (Risso, 1818)
WIRTZ (1995, 1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Family Scyllaeidae Fischer, 1883
- Scyllaea pelagica* Linné, 1758
SIMROTH (1888), MORTON ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Family Phylliroidae Férussac, 1821
- Phylliroe* cf. *atlantica* Bergh, 1871
WIRTZ (1998).
- Family Dotoidae Gray, 1853
- Doto floridicola* Simroth, 1888
SIMROTH (1888), WIRTZ (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Family Flabellinidae Bergh, 1889
- Flabellina pedata* (Montagu, 1815)
GOSLINER (1994), WIRTZ (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Family Facelinidae Bergh, 1889
- Caloria elegans* (Alder and Hancock, 1845)
MORO ET AL (1995), WIRTZ (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).
- Family Aeolidiidae D'Orbigny, 1834
- **Aeolidiella sanguinea* (Norman, 1877)
MORTON ET AL. (1998: 79), ÁVILA (2000).
- Spurilla neapolitana* Delle Chiaje, 1823
SIMROTH (1888) AND WIRTZ (1998). Cited by both authors as *S. sargassicola*.
- Family Glaucidae Menke, 1828
- Glaucus atlanticus* Forster, 1777
SIMROTH (1888), BERGH (1899), WIRTZ (1998).
- Family Fionidae Alder and Hancock, 1855
- Fiona pinnata* Eschscholtz, 1831
BERGH (1892 as *Fiona marina*), WIRTZ (1998), MORTON ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA ET AL. (1998), ÁVILA (2000).